

HARMLESS

Break out room

Safe and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA) & Decision Support System (DSS)

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Final Webinar
11 March 2025 Online

Outline

- **Poll topics for deeper discussion**
 - AMEA, WASP, ASDI, LICARA nanoScan 4.0 or SSbD-DSS & other tools, or
 - Other topics or questions (please, put them in the chat)
- **Access to the SSbD-DSS and start**
- **First topic(s) for deeper discussion**
- **Other topic(s) or questions**
 - Questions not addressed in the webinar will be answered via e-mail later
- **Wrapping up**

Poll topics for deeper discussion

- **AMEA - Step 1 of DSS - Categorization and design principles**
- **WASP - Step 2 of DSS - Early warning, design advice and assessment advice**
- **ASDI - Step 3 of DSS - Enter lab phase measurement values to assess best SSbD version**
- **LICARA nanoScan 4.0 - Step 4 of DSS - Multi-dimension assessment and Status wheel**
- **SSbD-DSS & other tools - How the DSS guides through other tools**
- **Other topic**
 - Please write the topic or question you want us to address in the chat
 - Questions not addressed in the webinar will be answered via e-mail later

Access to the HARMLESS SSbD-DSS

- The SSbD-DSS will be launched end April (publicly for free)
- Registering TODAY will give direct access to the pre-launch demo version
- After today & before public launch: Request access to pre-launch demo version
 - register and sent email to support.diamonds@tno.nl requesting access
- Go to <https://diamonds.tno.nl> and click

DIAMONDS

A GENERIC DATA MANAGEMENT AND INTEGRATION PLATFORM FOR THE LIFE SCIENCES

DIAMONDS brings together Data, Knowledge and Algorithms. Data ranges from Clinical studies and Omics data to Personalized Health data. Traceable from original Raw measurements to Cleaned, Processed data ready to use. Knowledge ranges from Biological Knowledge from Curated databases and Textmining to manually Curated Triples from our Experts. All captured and connected to Source information through Standardized Pipelines and Workflows Protocols. Diverse tools and algorithms such as Statistical tools, Text mining methods, Scripts, Decision Trees, Bayesian/Dynamic Networks and Network Visualization.

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DIAMONDS highlights

Summary of highlighted projects and modules in DIAMONDS

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Follow this link to register an account
and follow registration steps

Dashboard

Select a project ▾

Select a module ▾

Private projects

Currently, you do not have access to any private projects

If all went well, you'll see these publicly available tools after login

Publicly available tools

✓ TRAAC

TRAAC framework

✓ Nano Exposure Quantifier

The Nano Exposure Quantifier (NEQ) is a quantitative exposure assessment tool. It is designed to assist users in the safe-by-design process and decisions to reduce risk as a result from working with manufactured nanomaterials. The NEQ offers a Tiered approach by

! Contamination Estimate Calculator

The contamination estimate tool provides a first indication of the unintended allergen presence (UAP) in a product .

! Substance Information System

Welkom in het stoffeninformatiesysteem (SIS), een tool ontwikkeld door TNO en gefinancierd door ministerie SZW. SIS is ontwikkeld om een breed scala aan informatie over gevaarlijke stoffen bijeen te brengen. De tool bevat onder andere stofspecifieke informatie over

! ECEL 3.0

ECEL 3.0: An Integrated Risk Management Measure Library

! LICARA Innovation Scan

Project concerning the publicly available LICARA Innovation Scan

! Hotspot Scan

The Hotspot Scan is a public tool that allows a systematic and efficient assessment of potential hotspots in the life cycle of innovative products.

! AMEA 2.1 - Advanced Material Earliest Assessment

AMEA 2.1 is an online tool that helps industry with their safety assessment in the earlier phases of innovation. Through three simple questions, the user is rewarded with SSbD advice that is most suited to their material category.

! HARMLESS SSbD Decision Support System (Demo)

The HARMLESS project aims to develop a Decision Support System for Safe-by-Design for complex nano-materials and high-aspect ratio nano-materials. This project is used for demo purposes such as on 250311.

☰ WASP2.1 - Warning flags, design Advice & Screening Prior...

WASP 2.1 is an online tool to help industry with Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) in the ideation and business case phase. With only 12 (+3 optional) questions, the user a) gains insight in which areas require specific attention, b) gets advice on how to best change the

Click

This is the pre-launch demo version of the DSS

HARMLESS SSbD Decision Support System (Demo) modules

Scan

This scientific tool-building module allows to run diverse online scientific tools, e.g. LICARA Innovation Scan, StoffenManager Nano, HotSpot Scan, AMEA, WASP etc.

SSbD Decision Support System

The HARMLESS project aims to develop a Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design Decision Support System (SSbD-DSS) for complex- and high-aspect ratio nanomaterials.

Go to the Decision Support System (SSbD-DSS)

The Scan module allows you to run some individual tools as stand-alone tools but only recommended when you are more experienced.

SSbD-DSS Safe-&-Sustainable-by-Design Decision Support System

Quick start

1) Go to Projects

2) Create a new project

3) Complete form

4) Follow recommended action

Create a DSS Project and follow purple recommended actions

Iterate through the DSS-cycle

a) Perform an action (=run a tool/add data)

b) Inspect results & advice

c) Check updated recommended and/or optional actions

repeat a, b, c

Show Support

Poll topics for deeper discussion

- AMEA
- WASP
- ASDI
- LICARA nanoScan 4.0
- **SSbD-DSS & other tools**
- **Other topic**
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SSbD-DSS & other tools

SSbD-DSS & other tools

Nano Exposure Quantifier

A quantitative tool for assessing exposure in the workplace

The Nano Exposure Quantifier (NEQ) is a quantitative exposure assessment tool. It is designed to assist users in the safe-by-design process and decisions to reduce risk as a result from working with manufactured nanomaterials. The NEQ offers a Tiered approach by adapting the questions based on the depth of information the user can provide allowing anywhere between a Tier-1 and a Tier-2 approach.

Substance Information System

A Smart Search Engine Providing an Integrative View on occupational human health risk information.

Substance Information System (SIS) is a public tool developed on the TNO DIAMONDS platform that allows users to search and find information on hazardous substances. The tool collects and organizes information from diverse sources to provide an integrative resource on substance properties, safety, health effects, exposure, and application by business sectors.

Hotspot Scan

A SYSTEMATIC SCREENING TOOL FOR POTENTIAL HOTSPOTS IN THE LIFE CYCLE OF INNOVATIVE PRODUCTS

The Hotspot Scan is a public tool that allows a systematic and efficient assessment of potential hotspots in the life cycle of innovative products. To perform a full LCA can be a time-consuming and challenging task, the HotSpot Scan provides an intermediate assessment focusing on the strongest human health and environmental impacts based on establishing all the material flows.

ECEL 3.0

AN INTEGRATED RISK MANAGEMENT MEASURE LIBRARY

ECEL 3.0 is a public tool developed on the DIAMONDS platform that offers a searchable library of occupational and environmental Risk Management Measures (RMM). Supporting registrants to evaluate the quantitative effectiveness of a specific RMM or downstream users (industry, research, consulting) on the most suitable RMM for a given exposure or emission scenario.

DSS Project (over different innovation stages)

Overarching guidance

SSbD-DSS

ASDI

AMEA

WASP

LnS 4.0

SIS

NEQ

HotspotScan

Also as individual tools

A particular goal

Recommended DSS-workflow

Optional / advanced

The project dashboard shows three types of actions in sections below each other and in different colors

Recommended actions

Find below the currently most recommended actions to do. Below the available actions are presented in recommended order.

#1 AMEA - Advanced Material Earliest Assessment

Step #1 of the DSS Workflow.
With only 3 questions, **Advanced Material Earliest Assessment (AMEA) v2.1** helps to categorize the project, provides early SSbD advice on design principles and checks applicability to continue with the DSS.
(VERY EASY - 10min - Ideation/Busin. Phase)

Attach existing run > Start scan run >

#2 WASP - Warning, Advise & Screening Priorities

Step #2 of the DSS Workflow.
With only 14 questions, **Warning flags, design Advice & Screening Priorities (WASP) v2.1** indicates which areas require specific attention, provides further SSbD advice and recommends descriptors for the lab phase.
(EASY - 25min - Ideation/Business Phase)

Start scan run >

Purple tiles are the most recommended actions

Optional actions (future actions that are not yet applicable or actions recommended only for very experienced DSS users)

#2.5 Advance to Lab Phase

Stage Advancement as part of the DSS Workflow.
When AMEA and WASP are finalized and the "Ideation and Business Case Phase" successfully completed, advance this projects innovation stage to the **Lab Phase**.
(VERY EASY - 1min - Ideation/Business Phase)

>

#3 ASDI - Alternative SSbD Design Inspector

Step #3 of the DSS Workflow.
Specify your SSbD designs and descriptors in the **Design page**. Enter measured values to interactively visualize design differences and get relevant SSbD advice.
(MEDIUM - 45min - Lab Phase)

>

Hot Spot Scan - Construction Chemicals

Hot Spot Scan - Construction Chemicals

Start scan run >

Brown tiles are optional actions.
- It may be future actions that are **not yet** recommended, OR ...
- actions that are not part of the main DSS Workflow, but useful for experienced users

Completed actions

Specify industry

Specify the industry the product will be used in. This will determine which environmental release model (HotSpot Scan) is most relevant

Choose industry >

The choice of industry that we already filled in did determine the relevant Hot Spot Scan

White tiles are actions that have been completed. (e.g. we already specified the industry when we created the project, so that action is now completed)

Project 01-02-2023

HARMLESS SSbD-DSS

The HARMLESS project aims to develop a Decision Support System for Safe-by-Design for complex nano-materials and high-aspect ratio nano-materials.

[Read more](#)

Project 20-07-2023

AMEA 2.1 - Advanced Material Earliest Assessment

AMEA 2.1 is an online tool, developed by HARMLESS, that helps industry by means of three simple questions with their Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) choices for advanced materials (AdMa) in the earliest phases of innovation.

[Read more](#)

Project 10-12-2024

WASP 2.1 - Warning flags, design Advice & Screening Priorities

WASP 2.1 is an online tool to help industry with Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) in the ideation and business case phase. With only 12 (+3 optional) questions, the user a) gains insight in which areas require specific attention, b) gets advice on how to best change the design and c) gets advice on what assays and guidelines to follow and which descriptors to measure (in the lab phase).

[Read more](#)

	AdMa	CoMa	ReMa
Performance	Green	Red	White
Design space	Grey	Grey	Black
Human safety	Green	Red	Red
Env. safety	Red	Green	Red
Sustainability	Green	Red	White

Project 08-01-2021

ASDI – Alternative SSbD Design Inspector

assessment of benefits and risks for innovative products.

[Read more](#)

Project 08-01-2021

LICARA Innovation Scan 4.0

The LICARA Innovation Scan is a public tool that allows a preliminary but swift assessment of benefits and risks for innovative products.

[Read more](#)

new

Tier-1

Project 14-11-2022

Nano Exposure Quantifier

The Nano Exposure Quantifier (NEQ) is a quantitative exposure assessment tool. It is designed to assist users in the safe-by-design process and decisions to reduce risk as a result from working with manufactured nanomaterials. The NEQ offers a Tiered approach by adapting... provide allowing any...

[Read more](#)

Exposure model

Hazard

Project 03-07-2018

Substance Information System

Substance Information System (SIS) is a public tool developed on the TNO DIAMONDS platform that allows users to search and find information on hazardous substances. The tool collects and organizes... provide an integrative resource on substance exposure, and application by business...

[Read more](#)

Hazard & Exposure of a Compound

Photo by thr3_eyes on Unsplash

Project 07-07-2021

Hotspot Scan

The Hotspot Scan is a public tool that allows a systematic and efficient assessment of potential hotspots in the life cycle of innovative products. To perform a full LCA can be a time-consuming and challenging task, the HotSpotScan provides an intermediate assessment focusing on the strongest human health and environmental impacts based on establishing all the material flows.

[Read more](#)

Environmental release

Project 11-09-2019

ECEL 3.0

ECEL 3.0 is a public tool developed on the DIAMONDS platform that offers a searchable library of occupational and environmental Risk Management Measures (RMM). Supporting registrants to evaluate the quantitative effectiveness of a specific RMM or downstream users (industry, research, consulting) on the most suitable RMM for a given exposure or emission scenario.

[Read more](#)

Efficacy of Risk Management Measures

Project 20-10-2022

TRAAC

The TRAAC framework is developed to quantify the readiness of different tools and methods towards their wider regulatory acceptance and downstream use by different stakeholders. The framework diagnoses barriers which hinder regulatory acceptance and wider usability of a tool/method. It is based on their Transparency, Reliability, Accessibility, Applicability and Completeness (TRAAC).

[Read more](#)

Readiness of models/tools

Risk Management Scenario: Bevochtigen / doordrenken / afsluiten tijdens breken

#	468
Name	Bevochtigen / doordrenken / afsluiten tijdens breken
Description	Overzicht effectiviteit van bevochtigen, doordrenken of afsluiten van materialen tijdens breken.

Info about this scenario

Created by	Birgit van Duuren
Created at	2022-04-11 12:10:37
Updated by	Birgit van Duuren
Updated at	2023-03-28 20:58:33

Selection info

Results	Value
Number of available records	64
Number of selected records	64
Number of selected studies	23
Effectiveness Lower 95% HDI	78%
Effectiveness Median	84.4%
Effectiveness Upper 95% HDI	87%

RMM analysis

ECEL – Risk Management Measures
Define filters and get distribution of efficiencies

This category provides information on possible adverse health effects of the compound, including hazard statements (H phrases), precautionary statements (P phrases), and symbols sourced from PubChem, which aggregates data from other authoritative sources including ECHA, HCIS, HSDB, NITE-CMC, and Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 (CLP Regulation).

[CLP-icons](#)

Hazard bands	
Eye damage	E
Inhalation	E
Local skin damage	E
Skin uptake systemic	E
Overall	E
Classifications	
Flam. Liq. 2	
Asp. Tox. 1	
Skin Irrit. 2	
Eye Irrit. 2	
Muta. 1B	
Carc. 1A	
STOT RE 1	
Aquatic Chronic 3	(16%)

Hazard Statements (H-phrases)	Hazard bands			
	Eye damage	Inhalation	Local skin damage	Skin uptake systemic
H225 Highly flammable liquid and vapour.				
H302 Harmful if swallowed.	B			B
H304 May be fatal if swallowed and enters airways.	B	A		
H315 Causes skin irritation.	C	B	B	
H319 Causes serious eye irritation.	C	B	A	
H332 Harmful if inhaled.	B	B		
H335 May cause respiratory irritation.	C	B	A	
H336 May cause drowsiness or dizziness.	B	B		
H340 May cause genetic defects.	E	E	E	E
H341 Suspected of causing genetic defects.	B	D	D	D
H350 May cause cancer.	E	E	E	E
H361 Suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child.				
H370 Causes damage to	B	B		B

Health effects (Health Effect Codes)	
HE1	cancer, currently regulated by OSHA as a carcinogen
HE12	Hematological Blood Disorders, Anemias
HE14	Irritant to eyes, nose, throat, skin, marked
HE7	Nervous system disorders, Nervous system effects other than narcosis
HE8	Nervous System Disorders, Narcosis

Precautionary measures (P-phrases)	
P203	Obtain, read and follow all safety instructions before use
P210	Keep away from heat, hot surfaces, sparks, open flames and other ignition sources. No smoking.
P233	Keep container tightly closed.
P240	Ground and bond container and receiving equipment.
P241	Use explosion-proof electrical/ventilating/light/.../equipment.
P242	Use only non-sparking tools.
P243	Take action to prevent static discharges.
P260	Do not breathe dust/fume/gas/mist/vapours/spray.
P261	Avoid breathing dust/fume/gas/mist/vapours/spray.
P264	Wash ... thoroughly after handling.
P273	Avoid release to the environment.
P280	Wear protective gloves/protective clothing/eye protection/face protection.
P301+P316	IF SWALLOWED: Get emergency medical help immediately.
P301+P317	IF SWALLOWED: Get medical help.
P302+P352	IF ON SKIN Wash with soap and water.
P303+P361+P353	IF ON SKIN (or hair) Remove/Take off immediately all contaminated clothing. Rinse skin with water [or shower].

SIS – Substance Information System
 Search compound and find all kinds of information, such as physchem, hazard & exposure

Other pilot phase tools

More complex, quantitative models & testing methods (NAMs), such as:

- GRACIOUS Tier 2 testing methods
- In vitro NAMs
- Quantitative predictive exposure and hazard models

Future feature: Adding the outcomes of these models & methods to the Status Wheel by replacing or adding new segments

LICARA nanoScan 4.0

Project 07-07-2021

Hotspot Scan

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[Read more](#)

Project 14-11-2022

Nano Exposure Quantifier

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[Read more](#)

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Other topics & questions

Other topic or questions

Where can we receive the whole pdf presentation?

The recording, summary and link to the pdf of the presentations can be found at our website:

<https://www.harmless-project.eu/recap-harmless-final-webinar-11-03-2025-online/>

What tools are included in the detailed assessment? If I understood well AMEA, WASP, LICARA are for early screening?

AMEA and WASP are meant for the early innovation phases

ASDI is meant for the lab-phase

LICARA 4.0 can be used in the early pilot phase

More complex and quantitative assays and predictive models are recommended for the pilot phase

Does the Hotspot analysis consider multiple applications, or only the ones as case studies in the project?

The AMEA and WASP tools can be used to identify hotspots or potential safety and sustainability concerns in the early innovation stages. These tools are applicable for advanced materials which are either nano-enabled or consist or contain particles.

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Wrapping up

Wrapping-up (slides not presented but added for your information).

- Are you interested in a follow-up meeting to discuss potential use of the HARMLESS DSS or tools?
 - Please, send an e-mail to susan.dekkers@tno.nl or eugene.vansomeren@tno.nl, so we can contact you.

More information?

Visit the HARMLESS website:

<https://www.harmless-project.eu/>

Visit the DIAMONDS website (also to register for DSS):

<https://diamonds.tno.nl/>

Email: support.diamonds@tno.nl

Before end April (= public launch):
Register and then sent email requesting
prelaunch access (see also sheet 4)

Preprints of our publications the SSbD approach and DSS:

<https://doi.org/10.22541/au.174077018.85147151/v1>

<https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173991289.98651419/v1>

This project has received EU funding from under grand agreement No 953183.

Future perspectives DSS

- **Further development pilot phase methods and tools**
- **Possible use of EWS in OECD Early4AdMa Tier 1**
- **Develop customized tools for industrial companies (e.g. BASF)**
- **Develop non-particle specific tools (e.g. PLANETS)**

Thanks for your attention!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953183

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